

Undeniable proof for the existence fourth (space) dimension

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Abstract: The title has been changed **from** “*Test for undeniable proof of (the existence of) the fourth space (spatial) dimension*” **to** “*Undeniable proof for the existence fourth space dimension*” today (10 January 2026). The test which this article has been advocating has [already been observed in 2023 with 7 sigma significance](#). Please click hyperlink and read the article. [For more technical information, kindly read [Ref A](#) and [Ref B](#)]. Kindly note that the tetrahedrons (mentioned in above article) have been drawn using imaginary lines. Hence the 3D tetrahedrons are pure geometry and not material objects. This implies that the geometry of SpaceTime itself shows chiral asymmetry (even at galactic scales!). Unlike the chiral asymmetry appearing in weak interactions, this cannot be dismissed as inherent chiral asymmetry of the force, since there is no force involved here. It is plain geometry!

Honestly, the [concept of SpaceTime needs a major revision to rescue both physics and cosmology from crisis](#). SpaceTime is actually a [3D hypersurface, which is embedded in 4D space, and is moving in the fourth dimension](#). The above mentioned does not validate cosmic inflation. However, it does imply that in the distant past the universe changed from a 4D hypersphere (solid cricket ball structure) to an expanding 3D hypersurface of an (imaginary) 4D hypersphere (expanding, hollow football structure).

Achiral Meta-Atoms have a strong chiral response, which can be used as direct evidence for the existence of the fourth space (spatial) dimension. [**Updates: 1**) James Webb Telescope (JWST) has found that vast majority of galaxies rotate in the same direction. This chiral asymmetry **does not** mean that the entire universe is rotating. It does **not mean** that the universe is inside a black hole. This chiral asymmetry strongly hints at extra space dimension. **2**) Quasicrystals are, in fact, periodic—but in a higher dimension than the one in which they exist physically. [Scientists glimpse 4D crystal structure using surface wave patterns](#).]

Introduction:

Letters such as P and F and their mirror images are non-superposable by translation or rotation in the 2D plane (of the paper). However, if they can be taken out of the 2D plane, and flipped over, then they become superposable with their mirror image.

A similar case arises in the 3D with handedness. Left hand and right hand are mirror images, which are non-superposable by any amount of translation or rotation in 3D. However, in this case it is not possible (for humans) to move it out of 3D into the 4th space dimension and do a flip over. If it could be done, then there would have been no question about the existence of the fourth space (spatial) dimension.

Nature has been very strongly hinting about the existence of the fourth space (spatial) dimension. Some of those are indirect evidences include:

1) Hints of the 4th space (spatial) dimension have already been detected by two separate research teams, one in the US and one in Europe [**Ref. 1, 2**]. Both of these experiments utilized a phenomenon known as the quantum Hall effect. Results strongly hinted that the true geometry of nature is 4D.

2) Nature's true geometry is also revealed and demonstrated by the 'Principle of Least Action (PLA)', from which ALL KNOWN laws of physics can be derived. PLA can be generalized to the 'Principle of Maximum Proper Time', which reduces to a shockingly simple statement: "The least distance between two points in 4D (hyper) space is a straight line". That should be sufficient to convince any scientist, but nature goes farther still.

3) [Kaluza's miracle](#) of obtaining Maxwell's equations in addition to Einstein's field equations [Ref.11] seemed to exact a heavy price: A fifth dimension was needed as an embedding space. However, four dimensions are sufficient (and electromagnetic phenomena are obtained as bonus). The 4th dimension was mistaken for a fifth dimension because of improper understanding of imaginary numbers.

[NOTE: Before claiming that evidences and observations points against any embedment in a higher dimension space (i.e. 4th space dimension), readers should kindly note that most of the objections (like absence of infinite towers of particles required for validation of Kaluza-Klein theory, which is a membrane theory in a higher dimension embedment) are based on wrong assumption of Oscar Klein. His analogy of embedment in a higher dimensional space with a hose-pipe (having a physically curled-up dimension) has pushed physics away from a miraculous unification to a blind alley. Even, the logics like "Forces fall off with the square of distance, not the cube" and "One can block cubes by surrounding them on 6 sides, without needing to block 24 sides" fail to disprove the existence of 4th space dimension, because every particle and every force (including gravity) are confined within the 3D (hyper) surface of the hyperballoon universe [Ref. 3]. And most importantly, very soon Euclid telescope or the DESI (Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument) team can conclusively find out whether the universe is embedded in a 4th space dimension or not. **Only a plot of number of galaxies versus distance is needed.** If the universe is 3D flat, then the number of galaxies should be proportional to the square of radius, while if the 3D space curves in the 4th space dimension, then the number to deviate (become lesser) from former prediction with increasing radius.]

4) Nature has been discriminating between the real thing and its mirror image in weak interaction. This discovery shocked the physics world, and won a Nobel Prize.

Nature has also been discriminating between left handed and right handed molecules in biology.

However all these have been dismissed as non-related to the existence of a 4th dimension since these are microscopic effects and intrinsic property of chiral molecules themselves. But there is a direct test possible.

Method and Experiment

Recently, researchers have shown that achiral meta-atoms have a strong chiral response [Ref. 4], which can be used as direct evidence for the existence of the fourth space (spatial) dimension.

The researchers used achiral meta-atoms placed on a substrate and arranged in a monoclinic lattice (a lattice whose unit cell has unequal side lengths and interior angles not equal to 90 degree). The mirror

symmetry of this system is broken in the plane parallel to the lattice by the monoclinic geometry and in the plane perpendicular to the lattice by the presence of the substrate. They used achiral meta-atoms in the form of silicon cylinders and a silicon oxide substrate.

They found that the system was more transparent to circularly polarized light of one handedness than it was to the other.

They have in effect created handedness using non-chiral molecules. And what is really worthwhile to note is that it is not a microscopic system anymore. The substrate can be made quite thick (maybe a few centimeters or inches thick), and also the silicon cylinders can be made similarly long.

Just by reversing the position of the substrate on the monoclinic lattice (i.e. placing the substrate above the lattice instead of below the lattice, the handedness of the system can be changed.

Conclusion:

If the response to circularly polarized light gets reversed, then it will be undeniable proof that nature is indeed discriminating between left and right handedness even at the macro-scale, which is clear and undeniable proof of (the existence of) the fourth space (spatial) dimension.

Reference:

- 1) Lohse, M., Schweizer, C., Price, H. et al. Exploring 4D quantum Hall physics with a 2D topological charge pump. Nature 553, 55–58 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature25000>
- 2) Zilberberg, O., Huang, S., Guglielmon, J. et al. Photonic topological boundary pumping as a probe of 4D quantum Hall physics. Nature 553, 59–62 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature25011>
- 3) Subhajit Waugh. Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity are compatible, and have a common origin: the expanding (hyper) balloon universe. Authorea. December 04, 2022.
DOI: 10.22541/au.165888607.78422236/v9
- 4) I. Toftul et al., “Chiral dichroism in resonant metasurfaces with monoclinic lattices,” Phys. Rev. Lett. 133, 216901 (2024).